

Supporting Information

A nanohybrid for photodynamic therapy and fluorescence imaging tracking without therapy

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Experimental Procedures

Materials

Chemicals used for the UCNP's synthesis were lanthanide chlorides ($\text{YCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{YbCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ErCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{TmCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (>99.9%, all of them)), 1-octadecene (95%), oleic acid (70%), NaOH and NH_4F (99.99%). All these chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received without previous purification. Chemicals used for the synthesis of PP and NI were purchased from commercial sources and were of the highest grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard procedures

Experimental

Synthesis of 6-(6-(1,5-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)-1,3-dioxo-1H-benzo[de]isoquinolin-2(3H)-yl)hexanoic acid (**NI**).

Scheme S1. Synthetic route to **NI**. Reagents, conditions and yields: *i.* 6-aminohexanoic acid, EtOH, Δ , 85%; *ii.* PhCHO, NaOH, EtOH, H_2O , 0–5 °C, 35%; *iii.* PhNHNH₂, AcOH, Δ .

Synthesis of 4-Acetyl-1,8-naphthalic anhydride (1). Compound **1** was prepared by literature procedure starting from the commercially available acenaphthene.¹

Synthesis of 6-(6-acetyl-1,3-dioxo-1H-benzo[d,e]isoquinolin-2(3H)-yl)hexanoic acid (2).

To a suspension of compound **1** (200 mg, 0.83 mmol) and ethanol (7 mL) 6-aminohexanoic acid (0.174 g, 1.3 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 14 h to afford a transparent solution. The solution was cooled to ambient temperature and filtered off. The precipitate was washed with ethanol and dried to give 250 mg of **2** as a light-yellow solid with 85% yield. M.p. 122 – 124 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500.13 MHz, 25 °C, δ / ppm, *J* / Hz): 1.31 – 1.39 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.51 – 1.59 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.59 – 1.71 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 2.21 (t, 2H, CH_2COOH , *J* = 7.5), 2.80 (s, 3H, CH_3CO), 4.03 (t, 2H, CH_2N , *J* = 7.5), 7.94 (dd, 1H, H(6), *J* = 7.2, *J* = 8.6), 8.37 (d, 1H, H(3), *J* = 7.7), 8.50 – 8.57 (m, 2H, H(2), H(7)), 8.82 (dd, 1H, H(5), *J* = 8.6, *J* = 1.1), 10.58 (br s, 1H, COOH). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 125.76 MHz, 25 °C, δ / ppm): 24.21, 25.98, 27.15, 30.25, 33.49, 122.35, 124.77, 127.71, 127.92, 128.52, 129.68, 130.78, 132.01, 140.19, 162.77, 174.42, 201.66. EI-MS, *m/z* (I, %): 353 (50) [M]⁺, 294 (44), 253 (30), 252 (41), 240 (76), 238 (59), 225 (42), 224 (100), 222 (57), 153 (23). Elemental analysis: calculated (%) for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_5$ (MW 353.37): C 67.98, H 5.42, N 3.96; found C 67.89, H 5.32, N 3.92.

6-(1,3-dioxo-6-(3-phenylacryloyl)-1H-benzo[d,e]isoquinolin-2(3H)-yl)hexanoic acid (3).

A stirring mixture of **2** (600 mg, 1.7 mmol), benzaldehyde (230 μL , 0.26 mmol) and ethanol (5.5 mL) was cooled to 0 °C before 1.02 mL of 10% aqueous NaOH were added. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at ambient temperature, then diluted with water, acidified with 5% aqueous HCl to pH 3 and extracted with chloroform. Organic layer was washed with water and dried over Na_2SO_4 . After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, 265 mg of **3** were obtained (yield 35%). M.p. 124–126 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500.13 MHz, 25 °C, δ / ppm, *J* / Hz): 1.33 – 1.41 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.51 – 1.61 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.61 – 1.71 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 2.23 (t, 2H, CH_2COOH , *J* = 7.5), 4.06 (t, 2H, CH_2N , *J* = 7.5), 7.43 – 7.50 (m, 3H, Ph), 7.59 (d, 1H, PhCH , *J* = 16.3), 7.61 (d, 1H, $\text{PhCH}=\text{CH}$, *J* = 16.3), 7.79 – 7.84 (m, 2H, Ph), 7.94 (dd, 1H, H(6), *J* = 7.2, *J* = 8.4), 8.20 (d, 1H, H(3), *J* = 7.5), 8.54 – 8.58 (m, 2H, H(5), H(7)), 8.59 (d, 1H, H(2), *J* = 7.5), 11.99 (br s, 1H, COOH). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 125.76 MHz, 25 °C, δ / ppm): 24.20, 25.99, 27.19, 33.46, 122.51, 124.11, 126.44, 127.55, 127.91, 128.37, 129.03, 129.07, 129.83, 131.00, 131.24, 131.68, 134.10, 141.63, 147.21, 162.95, 163.29, 174.41, 194.15). MS, *m/z* (I, %): 441 (100) [M]⁺, 383 (17), 382 (60), 340 (87), 326 (78), 310 (25), 282 (23), 256 (47), 228 (31), 226 (18). Elemental analysis: calculated (%) for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_5$ (MW 441.48): C 73.46, H 5.25, N 3.17; found C 73.35, H 5.23, N 3.11.

6-(6-(1,5-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)-1,3-dioxo-1H-benzo[d,e]isoquinolin-2(3H)-yl)hexanoic acid (NI).

A stirring mixture of **3** (250 mg, 0.57 mmol), phenylhydrazine (110 μL , 1.13 mmol) and glacial acetic acid (3.0 mL) was heated at 100 °C under argon atmosphere for 6 h. Then, the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with dichloromethane several times. Combined organic phases were washed with water and dried over Na_2SO_4 . After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, the crude product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using toluene/methanol gradient mixture as eluent and recrystallized from methanol to give 274 mg of **NI**. Characterization data of **NI**. M.p. ≥ 207 °C with decomp. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 400.13 MHz, 22 °C, δ / ppm, *J* / Hz): 1.29 – 1.42 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.49 – 1.60 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 1.60 – 1.72 (m, 2H,

CH₂CH₂N), 2.22 (t, 2H, CH₂COOH, *J* = 7.2), 3.40 (dd, 1H, PhCHCH₂, *J* = 6.1, *J* = 17.1), 4.04 (t, 2H, CH₂N, *J* = 7.5), 4.23 (dd, 1H, PhCHCH₂, *J* = 12.3, *J* = 17.1), 5.68 (dd, 1H, PhCHCH₂, *J* = 6.1, *J* = 12.3), 6.78 – 6.87 (m, 1H, NPh), 7.11 – 7.20 (m, 2H, NPh), 7.20 – 7.31 (m, 3H, NPh, CPh), 7.32 – 7.53 (m, 4H, CPh), 7.90 (d, 1H, H(3), *J* = 7.8), 8.07 (dd, 1H, H(6), *J* = 7.5, *J* = 8.6), 8.45 (d, 1H, H(2), *J* = 7.8), 8.58 (d, 1H, H(7), *J* = 7.5), 9.92 (d, 1H, H(5), *J* = 8.6), 11.99 (br s, 1H, COOH). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150.93 MHz, 21 °C, δ / ppm): 24.21, 26.03, 27.24, 33.48, 40.04, 44.50, 62.25, 113.59, 119.87, 121.30, 122.44, 125.48, 125.94, 127.39, 127.64, 128.08, 128.21, 128.32, 129.13, 129.19, 129.27, 130.36, 130.60, 133.67, 134.17, 142.00, 143.10, 146.33, 162.94, 163.45, 174.44. EI-MS, *m/z* (I, %): 532 (36), 531 (100) [M]⁺, 429 (23), 416 (24), 415 (32). Elemental analysis: calculated (%) for C₃₃H₂₉N₃O₄ (MW 531.60): C 74.56, H 5.50, N 7.90; found C 74.33, H 5.52, N 8.01.

Synthesis of the *N*-aminobacterio-purpurinimide (PP)

PP were prepared following a previously reported protocol starting from Bacteriochlorophyll α .²⁻⁴

Synthesis of oleate-capped NaYF₄: Yb³⁺ (19%), Er³⁺ (2%), Tm³⁺ (1%) nanoparticles (UC_{YbErTm}@OA)

NaYF₄: Yb, Er, Tm nanoparticles were synthesized by following a previously reported protocol with some modifications.⁵ In a 50 mL round-bottom flask, YCl₃·6H₂O (0.78 mmol), YbCl₃·6H₂O (0.19 mmol), ErCl₃·6H₂O (0.018 mmol), TmCl₃·6H₂O (0.012 mmol), oleic acid (12 mL) and octadecene (15 mL) were stirred at 160 °C under N₂ until complete dissolution of lanthanides salts. Then, the solution was cooled to 110 °C and 10 mL of a methanol solution containing NaOH (2.5 mmol) and NH₄F (4.0 mmol) was slowly added into the flask. Methanol was removed at 100 °C under N₂ and continuous stirring. Finally, the reaction was heated at 305 °C under N₂ during one hour. After that, the solution was cooled down to room temperature and the nanoparticles were precipitated by centrifugation (9000 rpm, 15 min, 25 °C). Later on, the oleate-capped UCNPs were washed three times with (43.5:40.5:16 v/v) hexane/acetone/methanol solution and once with ethanol.

Synthesis of ligand-free NaYF₄: Yb³⁺ (19%), Er³⁺ (2%), Tm³⁺ (1%) nanoparticles (UC_{YbErTm})

Oleate ligand was removed from the nanoparticle surface by following a previously described protocol.⁶ Briefly, 100 mg of UC_{YbErTm}@OA were dispersed in 10 mL of HCl aqueous solution at pH 4 and stirred for 2 h. The reaction pH was maintained at 4 by addition of a 0.1 M HCl solution. After that, three extractions with diethyl ether were carried out in order to remove the free oleic acid. Then, ether phases were recombined and re-extracted with water followed by a re-extraction with ether of the combined water phases. Ligand-free nanoparticles were recovered by precipitation with acetone and subsequent centrifugation at 9000 rpm for 15 min (25 °C). Finally, UC_{YbErTm} were redispersed in MilliQ water.

Singlet oxygen generation monitored by a chemical probe: 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene) dimalonic acid (ABDA)

The singlet oxygen generation upon NIR irradiation was estimated by measuring the decrease of ABDA emission due to the formation of its endoperoxide. To that purpose, seven acetonitrile dispersions containing UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI (1.3 mg·mL⁻¹) and ABDA (4.2·10⁻⁵ M) were prepared and placed in quartz cuvettes (1x1 cm²). These dispersions were stirred in the darkness for 20 minutes. Then, the dispersions were irradiated with a CW 975 nm diode laser for 1, 3, 5, 10, 20, 40 and 90 minutes, respectively. After that, the dispersions were centrifuged (11000 rpm, 10 min, 25 °C) and the emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 380$ nm) of the supernatants were recorded. For comparative purposes, a solution of PP (0.4 mg·mL⁻¹) and ABDA (4.2·10⁻⁵ M) in acetonitrile was irradiated at 975 nm and its emission ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 380$ nm) was registered at different time intervals. Analogous experiment with an irradiation wavelength of 365 nm was carried out.

Equipments

Melting points. Melting points were measured on Melt-temp melting point electrothermal apparatus and were uncorrected.

Column chromatography. The reaction course and purity of the final products was followed by TLC on silica gel (DC-Alufolien Kieselgel 60 F₂₅₄, Merck). Column chromatography was conducted over silica gel (Kieselgel 60, particle size 0.063-0.200 mm, Merck).

Electron impact (EI). EI (70 eV) mass spectra were obtained from Finnigan Polaris Q instrument (ion-trap) in standard conditions.

Elemental analyses. Elemental analyses were carried out in the Microanalysis Laboratory of the A.N. Nesmeyanov Institute of Organoelement Compounds.

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on an Avance 400, Avance 500 and Avance 600 spectrometers (Bruker) operating at 400.13, 500.13 and 600.22 MHz (for ¹H) and 100.61, 125.76 and 150.93 MHz (for ¹³C) respectively. The measurements were performed in DMSO-*d*₆ solutions. The chemical shifts (given as δ) were determined with an accuracy of 0.01 ppm relative to the signals corresponding to the residual solvents and recalculated to the internal standard (TMS); the spin-spin coupling constants (*J*) were measured with an accuracy of 0.1 Hz. The assignment of ¹H signals is based on ¹H COSY, HMBC and HSQC NMR spectra.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained using a Jeol 1010 microscope operating at 100 kV equipped with an 8 Mpx digital camera AMT RX80. For the preparation of the UCNPs samples, 10 μ L of a 0.5 mg·mL⁻¹ solution of the UCNPs were left to dry under vacuum at room temperature on a formvar/carbon film supported on a 300 mesh copper grid. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images were recorded using a TECNAI G² F20 microscope operating at 200 kV (point resolution of 0.24 nm) and equipped with a CCD GATAN camera.

X-ray power diffraction (XRD). XRD analyses were performed on a Bruker D8 Advance A25 diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at a voltage of 40 kV and 30 mA, and a LynxEye detector. The powder diffraction pattern was scanned over the angular range of $2\text{-}80^\circ$ (2θ) with a step size of 0.020° , at room temperature.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The TGA analyses were carried out using a TG-TGA Pyris Diamond system with an operative temperature range $25\text{-}1100^\circ\text{C}$ and 0.1 microgram sensitivity. The samples were heated from 25 to 800°C , with an increase of $5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and under air flux of $50 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

Centrifugation. Centrifugation was carried out in an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5804 R.

Zeta Potential. The zeta potential (ζ) was measured in a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS and is given as an average of three independent measurements.

UV-Visible spectroscopy. UV-Vis spectra were recorded using a quartz cuvette ($1\times 1\times 4 \text{ cm}$) in a SECOMAN Uvi LightXT-5 spectrometer provided with Lab power junior software 3.05 version.

Photoluminescence steady state studies. Steady-state photoluminescence spectra were obtained at room temperature with a 2-nm slit width and $5 \text{ nm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ speed scan using a SLM AmingoBowmann series 2 (AB2) fluorometer (Microbeam, S.A.). The AB2 software (v. 5.5) was used to register the data. All spectra were acquired using triangular quartz cuvettes under air atmosphere in a front face set up. Up-conversion emission spectra were recorded by excitation at 975 nm using a CW 975 nm diode laser (Thorlabs L975P1WJ) as excitation source coupled to the fluorometer.

Multiphoton fluorescence imaging microscopy. Measurements were performed using an Olympus FV1000MPE laser scanning confocal microscope connected to an Olympus BX61WI upright microscope equipped with a $25\times$ water immersion objective (1.05 NA). This confocal microscope was equipped with a Mai Tai HP Deep See multiphoton laser (80 MHz) with a pulse width of 100 fs as an excitation source. The laser focused on the sample at the desired wavelength (880 or 980 nm) and laser transmissivity and the light dose were determined. The image was acquired by means of a $25\times 1.05 \text{ N.A.}$ Olympus dipping lens, appropriate emission filters and dwell time of $2 \mu\text{s}\cdot\text{pixel}^{-1}$ and a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels. Emission was detected with a 4 channel visible-range detector ($420\text{-}500/515\text{-}580/590\text{-}650/660\text{-}740$).

Cell imaging and therapy. SH-SY5Y cells (CRL-2266, ATCC[®]), a subline derived from the neuroblastoma cell line SK-N-SH, were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium/F-12 (DMEM/F-12) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 2 mM L-glutamine, $50 \text{ IU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ penicillin, and $50 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ streptomycin (all from ThermoFisher Technologies, MA, USA). The cells were seeded onto P-25 culture plates, allowed to grow at 37°C , $5\% \text{ CO}_2$ and 100% humidity for 24 h . The following day, the cells were harvested at 80% confluence and incubated with $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ UC_{YbErTm}@NI, UC_{YbErTm}@PEG, or vehicle (culture medium) for 4 h . Then, the amount of culture medium was minimized to $\sim 3 \text{ mL}$ in the plate in order to avoid competitive water absorption. A power-adjustable CW 975 nm diode laser (Thorlabs L975P1WJ) with a power output of 1 W , was collimated and used to irradiate a delimited area of the culture plates. The output power was measured with a power-meter at the exact distance of the irradiation area (Thorlabs PM100A) and next, the cells were irradiated for $0, 1.5, 3, 5$ or 7 min while being kept at 37°C . Subsequently, cell viability was assessed by using a LIVE/DEAD[®] Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit for mammalian cells (ThermoFisher Technologies), based on fluorescent dyes, was used to determine whether the treatment affected cell survival. Cells with compromised membranes exhibited red fluorescence from the live-cell impermeable nucleic acid stain ethidium homodimer-1 (EthD1; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 510\text{-}560 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 590 \text{ nm}$), whereas cells with intact cell membranes converted non-fluorescent calcein AM into bright green fluorescent calcein ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 450\text{-}490 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515\text{-}565 \text{ nm}$) by using non-specific cytosolic esterases.

Fluorescence photomicrographs were acquired using a Zeiss Axiovert 40 CFL inverted microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany), in the $515\text{-}565 \text{ nm}$ and $590\text{-}740 \text{ nm}$ ranges for green (calcein AM) and red (EthD1), respectively. Images were adjusted for brightness and contrast and analyzed with Fiji imaging software.^[6] The number of living vs. dead cells was quantified in the microscope's field located exactly in the center of the irradiated area, and compared to not irradiated zones ($n=3\text{-}4$ replicates per condition).

Cellular morphology after treatment was assessed by seeding cells on 4-well Permanox[®] chamber slides (Nalgene Nunc International, Naperville, IL). The following day, the cells were incubated with $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni, UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG, or vehicle for 4 h , irradiated at 975 nm as described above, and subsequently fixed in 3.5% glutaraldehyde in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PB) for 1 h at 37°C . Cells were post-fixed in 2% OsO₄ for 1 h at room temperature, and stained in 2% uranyl acetate for 2 h 30 min at 4°C in the dark. Cells were then rinsed in distilled water, dehydrated in ethanol, and embedded overnight in Durcupan resin (Fluka, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA). Following polymerization, serial semithin sections ($1.5 \mu\text{m}$) were cut with a UC-6 ultramicrotome (Leica, Heidelberg, Germany) and lightly stained with 1% toluidine blue. Digital photomicrographs were acquired using a Nikon Eclipse E800 microscope. Ultrathin sections ($70\text{-}80 \text{ nm}$) were prepared on formvar copper grids and stained with lead citrate (Reynolds' solution). Ultrathin sections were studied at 80 kV using a FEI Tecnai G² Spirit transmission electron microscope (FEI Europe, Eindhoven, Netherlands) equipped with a Morada digital camera (Olympus Software Image Solutions GmbH, Münster, Germany).

Cell tracking of nanohybrid-treated cells was achieved by incubating the cells in similar conditions to those described above. Cells were then fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde, mounted, and coverslipped using FluorSave[™] reagent (Millipore, MA, USA). Photomicrographs were acquired by using an Olympus FV1000MPE confocal vertical microscope and a Nikon Eclipse i80 couple to a Nikon DS-Qi1 CMOS camera. Fluorescent emission after excitation at 975 nm was detected using the following filters: $515\text{-}580 \text{ nm}$ and $590\text{-}650 \text{ nm}$. All images were analyzed using Fiji software.⁷

Cytotoxicity assays. *In vitro* cytotoxicity of the nanohybrids was evaluated using an XTT Cell Proliferation Kit II (Roche, Mannheim, Germany) in SH-SY5Y cells growing in the same conditions as described above. Cells were seeded on a 96-well plate at a density of

3·10⁴ cells per well and cultured for 24 h. Culture medium was then replaced with different concentrations of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI or UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG (0, 25, 100, 250 and 500 gr·mL⁻¹) diluted in fresh culture medium, and the cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ for another 24 h. The following day, XTT reagent (50 µL; 0.3 mg·mL⁻¹) was added to each well and the plate was incubated at 37 °C for 4 h. Subsequently, absorbance at 450 nm was measured with a standard scanning multi-well spectrophotometer (ThermoScientific). Eight replicates (n=8) were performed for each condition. The viability of untreated cells was assumed to be 100%, while relative viability (%) of treated cells was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Cell viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{mean of } A_{450} \text{ value of treated group}}{\text{mean of } A_{450} \text{ value of control group}} \times 100$$

Equation S3.

Statistical analysis. Data are presented as mean ± SEM. Differences between groups were assessed by one-way ANOVA with one variable (treatment) followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. Differences were regarded as statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table S1. Comparison between the PDT *in vitro* performance of the last relevant UCNP-based photodynamic agents and of that of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI (in grey).

Emitter	PS	Absorbance range (nm)	Power density (W·cm ⁻²)	Nanohybrid dose (µg·ml ⁻¹)	Irradiation time (min)	Light dose (J·cm ⁻²)	Efficacy ^a (%)
Er ³⁺ 8	PpIX	300-450 500-650	1	200	15	900	60-70
Er ³⁺ 9	MC540	400-600	1.5	100	20	1800	40-80
Er ³⁺ 10	ZnPc	600-700	1	200	10	600	72
Er ³⁺ 11	SPCD	550-700	1.5	10	10	900	50-80
Er ³⁺ 12	RB	450-600	4	200	5	1200	50-60
Er ³⁺ 13	RB ZnPc	450-600 600-700	0.25	100	120	1800	10
Er ³⁺ , Tm ³⁺ 14	RB	450-600	0.5	166	10	300	26
Er ³⁺ , Tm ³⁺	PP	300-450 500-600 750-850	0.02	100	7	8.7	70-76

^a Calculated as % of cell death. ZnPc: zinc phthalocyanine; MC540: Merocyanine 540; PpIX: Photoporphyrin IX; SPCD: Silicon; phthalocyanine dihydroxide; RB: Rose Bengal.

Results and Discussion

Figure S1. A) TEM image of UC_{YbErTm}@OA (17.6±1.2 x 23.1±1.1 nm), B) TEM image of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI, C) the size distribution histogram, D) HRTEM image of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG.

Dual fluorescence of NI

NI is a dual-emissive 1,8-naphthalimide. NI orange emission ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 490 \text{ nm}$; 12%) can be ascribed to the coplanar configuration while the short-wavelength emission can result from the near orthogonal conformation between the naphthalimide and the pyrazolyl substituent. Thus, both a greenish-blue and an orange emission after excitation at the NI UV band ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} 365 \text{ nm}$) and an orange emission at 490 nm after excitation at the VIS band ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} 490 \text{ nm}$) are detected (for other dual-emissive 1,8-naphthalimides).¹⁵

Figure S2. Top: Structures of NI. Bottom: Absorption spectrum (dashed line) and emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$ black line; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 490 \text{ nm}$ red line) of NI in acetonitrile.

Figure S3. Left: Absorption spectrum (dashed line) and emission spectrum at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365$ nm (black line) of the PP in acetonitrile. Right: Emission spectrum of PP at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 800$ nm in acetonitrile. PP exhibited strong absorption in the 300-450 nm range ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 360$ and 420 nm), a peak at 550 nm and absorption in the 675-860 nm region ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 820$ nm, shoulder at 750 nm).

Figure S4. Emission spectra at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm of a $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ dispersion of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}$ (black line) and $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@NI$ (red line) in acetonitrile. Inset: magnification of the $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@NI$ spectrum. Spectra normalized at 650 nm.

Figure S5. TGA heating curve of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/NI$ expressed as weight (%) as a function of applied temperature together with the corresponding first derivative.

Figure S6. A) $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/PEG$ absorption spectrum in water. B) Emission spectra at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm of a $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ dispersion of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}$ (black line) and $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/PEG$ in water (red line) normalized at 650 nm. Inset: Picture of an aqueous dispersion of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/PEG$. Spectra normalized at 650 nm.

Figure S7. Emission spectra at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm of UC_{YbEr} (black line) and UC_{YbEr}@PP (red line) in acetonitrile; 55% a quenching of the emission below 600 nm and a new band at 835 nm were observed due to the presence of PP on the UCNP surface. Spectra normalized at 650 nm.

Figure S8. Inter-molecular quenching of NI emission at 445 nm in the presence of increasing amounts of PP. Fluorescence intensity was corrected on the primary inner filter effect.¹⁶

Figure S9. Fitted kinetic of the PL (between 515 and 580 nm) of UC_{YbErTm} ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm).

Table S2. Decay times obtained from the fitting of three different UC_{YbErTm} kinetics.

Kinetic	$\tau_{\text{decay}} / \mu\text{s}$	R^2
1	53.4	0.9882
2	63.6	0.9870
3	63.7	0.9813
Average	60.2 ± 0.9	

Figure S10. Fitted kinetic of the PL (between 515 and 580 nm) of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm).

Table S3. Decay times obtained from the fitting of three different UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI kinetics.

Kinetic	$\tau_{\text{decay}} / \mu\text{s}$	R^2
1	27.5	0.9899
2	28.8	0.9892
3	29.2	0.9883
Average	28.5 ± 0.9	

Figure S11. Fitted kinetic of the PL (between 515 and 580 nm) for UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm).

Table S4. Decay times obtained from the fitting for three different UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG kinetics.

Kinetic	$\tau_{\text{decay}} / \mu\text{s}$	R^2
1	56.1	0.9926
2	55.2	0.9911
3	54.3	0.9904
Average	55.2 ± 0.9	

Figure S12. Confocal image at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975 \text{ nm}$ and a dwell time of $2 \mu\text{s} \cdot \text{pixel}^{-1}$ of A) UC_{YbErTm}, B) UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and C) UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG monitored in the 515-580 range

Figure S13. Comparison between the absorption spectrum of PP in acetonitrile A) before (black circles) and after 490 nm irradiation under air for 90 min (red line) Inset: Emission intensity ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 600 \text{ nm}$) of PP over irradiation time. B) Comparison between the absorption spectrum of PP in acetonitrile before (black line) and after 975 nm irradiation under air for 90 min (red line). Inset: Absorption of PP at 547 nm in acetonitrile over irradiation time.

Figure S14. Comparison between the absorption spectra of Ni in acetonitrile before (black line) and after irradiation at A) 490 nm or B) 975 nm under air for 90 min (red line). Insets: Emission intensity ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 633 \text{ nm}$) of Ni in acetonitrile over irradiation time under air atmosphere.

Figure S15. Right: Comparison between the absorption spectrum of A) UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI or B) UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG dispersed in acetonitrile before (black line) and after NIR irradiation under air for 120 min (red line). Insets: Variation of the emission intensity ($\lambda_{em} = 823\text{nm}$) of the corresponding nano hybrid over irradiation time.

Figure S16. Comparison between UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI before (black line) and after 48 h in a typical culture medium (phenol red free); A) absorption spectra, B) emission spectra $\lambda_{ex} = 975\text{ nm}$, C) emission spectra $\lambda_{ex} = 490\text{ nm}$.

Figure S17. A) Decrease in ABDA emission intensity overtime due to singlet oxygen generation upon NIR irradiation of nano hybrid UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI. Decrease in ABDA emission intensity at 430 nm for B) nano hybrid UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI and C, D) PP upon 975 and 365 nm irradiation up to 90 min.

Figure S18. UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG do not display toxicity at moderate concentrations. (Right) An important decrease in cell viability was observed (17.32%; $p < 0.001$; $n=8$) only at the highest concentration (500 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI after 24 h culturing (Middle) or at concentrations $> 250\text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ after 48 h culturing (Left). UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG was harmless even at the highest dose assayed. Cell viability was tested by the XTT assay. Data shown as mean \pm SEM of eight replicates; *** $p < 0.001$.

Internalization studies. Electronic microscopy images of cells incubated with $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/\text{NI}$ in the culture medium for 4 h did not show nanoparticles associated to any vesicles and therefore the nanoparticles seemed to be internalized via a no vesicular transport (this seems unfeasible for a non-molecular species). The hypothesis is that internalization of the UCNPs could be mediated by small endosomes followed by its delivery into the cell cytoplasm.

Figure S19. Internalization of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@PP/\text{NI}$ is not mediated by vesicular transport. (A) Electron microscopy imaging revealed that the UCNPs suspended in culture medium were unspecifically uptaken by SH-SY5Y cells. Abundant groups of particles were found free in the cytoplasm. (B) Higher magnification images did not display any sign of vesicular transport of particles (arrows) across the cell membrane. Scale bars, 500 nm.

Figure S20. Comparison between the confocal images at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975 \text{ nm}$ and a dwell time of $2 \mu\text{s}\cdot\text{pixel}^{-1}$ of $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}@OA$, monitored in the 515-580 range (A) and 590-650 range (B), and of NI monitored in the 515-580 range (C) and 590-650 range (D). Scale bar: 50 μm .

Figure S21. Confocal images at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 880 \text{ nm}$ and a dwell time of $2 \mu\text{s}\cdot\text{pixel}^{-1}$ of SH-SY5Y cells incubated with NI monitored in the 590-650 nm range. Scale bar 20 μm .

Table S5. Quantification of the cell viability at different irradiation times; SH-SY5Y cells incubated in presence of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI irradiated at 975 nm for different times. Cell viability was tested by using Cell LIVE/DEAD@ Kit (damaged cells: red and intact cells: green).

using Cell LIVE/DEAD@ Kit (damaged cells: red and intact cells: green)

MOCK 0 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	217	0	0.00%	100.00%
Sample 2	368	2	0.54%	99.46%
Sample 3	256	5	1.92%	98.08%
Mean	280.33	2.33	0.82%	99.18%

0 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	270	5	1.82%	98.18%
Sample 2	332	8	2.35%	97.65%
Sample 3	420	10	2.33%	97.67%
Sample 4	221	2	0.90%	99.10%
Mean	310.75	6.25	1.85%	98.15%

1.5 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	354	16	4.32%	95.68%
Sample 2	249	9	3.49%	96.51%
Sample 3	411	71	14.73%	85.27%
Sample 4	224	18	7.44%	92.56%
Mean	309.5	28.5	7.50%	92.50%

3 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	313	40	11.33%	88.67%
Sample 2	158	122	43.57%	56.43%
Sample 3	250	169	40.33%	59.67%
Sample 4	285	183	39.10%	60.90%
Mean	251.5	128.5	33.58%	66.42%

5 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	110	310	73.81%	26.19%
Sample 2	62	248	80.00%	20.00%
Sample 3	159	250	61.12%	38.88%
Mean	110.33	269.33	71.64%	28.36%

7 min	Number of living cells	Number of dead cells	Killing efficiency	Cell survival
Sample 1	57	134	70.16%	29.84%
Sample 2	75	220	74.58%	25.42%
Sample 3	56	180	76.27%	23.73%
Mean	62.67	178.00	73.67%	26.33%

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